

216 | Trusting artificial intelligence: Comparative analysis of chatbot-generated and official guideline recommendations for treating depression in epilepsy patients

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Purpose: Large language models (LLMs), which form the basis of chatbots, possess the ability to emulate human language and rapidly produce responses that appear detailed and coherent. However, these features may mask the potential for chatbots to disseminate inaccurate information. Given the frequency with which patients turn to the internet for self-education, it is inevitable that some will rely on LLM-powered chatbots to seek medical information. This reliance could lead to the creation and propagation of misinformation.

Our objective was to evaluate the alignment of ChatGPT's recommendations for the medical treatment of depression in adults with epilepsy with established ILAE guidelines.

Method: We created a zero-shot prompt template for inquiring about treatment recommendations. This template enabled the generation of 15 questions, aligned with the 2022 ILAE guidelines. Each question underwent three iterations. Our evaluation compared responses obtained with and without the use of prompt engineering techniques, which involve specifying roles, tasks, and instructions. These prompts were randomly fed into the ChatGPT-4 model through the OpenAI interface. The responses from ChatGPT were categorised into four groups: compatible, compatible but insufficient, partially incompatible, and incompatible with the guidelines.

Results: ChatGPT consistently employed a methodical strategy in responding to queries, frequently advising users to seek individualised guidance tailored to a patient's unique health requirements and situation. Nevertheless, when presented with prompts lacking explicit directives, ChatGPT's answers often range from partially to completely incompatible with the guidelines. Conversely, when queries were crafted using precise prompt engineering techniques, the responses from ChatGPT predominantly aligned with the guidelines, albeit they were typically adequate yet insufficient.

Conclusion: Medical treatment of depression in adults with epilepsy is highly individualized. Although ChatGPT

provides detailed and clear answers, it should not replace the personalized care provided by healthcare professionals.

335 | Stigma determining factors in patients with epilepsy

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Purpose: To find factors determining the stigma in people with epilepsy (PWE) living in Belgrade, Serbia.

Method: Consecutive adult patients with a diagnosis of epilepsy able to understand and complete the questionnaires were included in the study. Patients completed the Serbian version of the Stigma Scale of Epilepsy (SSE) (Lalatovic et al. 2023), Neurological Disorders Depression Inventory for Epilepsy (NDDI-E), Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9), and Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7). A two-sample t-test was used to detect the effects of sociodemographic and epilepsy-related variables on stigma, and Pearson's coefficient for correlation between mood-related variables and stigma scores. By stepwise regression analysis, the major factors associated with stigma perception among PWE were identified.

Results: The sample consisted of 108 PWE (60.2% were female, age range: 19–67 years). Adverse effects of antiseizure medications (ASMs) ($t(106)=2.07, p=0.04, d=0.48$) and driving ability ($t(45)=2.90, p=0.006, d=0.85$) significantly influenced SSE scores. Other socio-demographic and clinical variables had no significant effects on epilepsy-related stigma. Depression severity significantly influenced SSE scores (based on the NDDI-E cut-off score), and SSE showed a positive association with PHQ-9 ($r=0.42, p<0.001$) and GAD-7 scores ($r=0.35, p<0.001$) as well. All potential predictor variables that showed a significant relationship with SSE (driving ability, adverse effects of ASMs, depression, and anxiety levels) were included in the stepwise regression analysis. Depression severity measured by PHQ-9 remained the only significant predictor of the SSE total score ($F(1,45)=10.01, p=0.003$). PHQ-9 accounted for 16.4% of the variance in the SSE total score.

Appendix

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